

UBUNTU-INSPIRED DISCIPLINE: RESTORING LEARNER BEHAVIOUR IN TSHWANE WEST DISTRICT SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the potential of Ubuntu-inspired discipline to address learner behaviour in Tshwane West District secondary schools. It responds to the growing need for alternative disciplinary measures as current approaches have proven ineffective in curbing violent and disruptive behaviours among learners. Employing a qualitative ethnographic research design, the study examines the influence of cultural values on learner behaviour. Data were collected through observations, individual interviews, and group interviews with learners and teachers from eight purposefully selected schools. Glasser's Choice Theory serves as a theoretical framework, offering insights into how Ubuntu values can enhance disciplinary practices. The findings underscore the inadequacy of existing measures to change learner behaviour, highlighting the critical role of Ubuntu values such as respect, empathy, morality, care, and tolerance in fostering positive behaviour. Participants advocated for integrating these values into school disciplinary frameworks to promote a compassionate, respectful, and culturally aligned approach to discipline. The study concludes that restoring Ubuntu-inspired discipline can significantly improve the learning environment and reduce incidents of violence. It recommends embedding Ubuntu values into school policies as an effective strategy for transforming learner behaviour and fostering a morally guided school culture. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of culturally relevant approaches to discipline in South African schools, offering a practical and ethical pathway to address behavioural challenges.

Keywords: *discipline ethnography, learner behaviour, Ubuntu, violence reduction*

1. INTRODUCTION

South Africa's rich tapestry of indigenous philosophies and cultural practices positions Ubuntu as a cornerstone of its societal framework. Ubuntu philosophy is an African ethical framework that emphasises the interconnectedness of individuals within a community and the inherent value of human relationships. [1] explains that the term 'Ubuntu' originates from the

word 'umuntu,' which translates to 'a human being' in the southern African Nguni languages (including isiXhosa, isiZulu, isiNdebele, and isiSwati). In the Tshivenda language, another indigenous South African language, 'muthu' is translated as 'human being.' Rooted in the idea that "I am because we are," Ubuntu underscores the importance of compassion, empathy, and mutual respect in fostering a harmonious society ([2]. This philosophy advocates for a holistic approach to human existence, where individual well-being is intrinsically linked to the well-being of others, promoting a sense of collective responsibility and shared humanity [9]. Ubuntu can create a basis for dialogue and mutually enhancing discourse between global bioethics and indigenous cultures [3]. When applied effectively, Ubuntu provides a "culturally responsive behavioural method that not only resonates with indigenous learners but also with those from diverse cultural backgrounds" [4]. This study examines the role of Ubuntu-inspired discipline in restoring learner behaviour in Tshwane West District secondary schools. By embedding Ubuntu values of respect, empathy, and interconnectedness, schools can create inclusive and supportive environments, addressing behavioural challenges through culturally relevant and transformative approaches. From a pedagogical approach, Ubuntu has the potential to safeguard and uphold traditional knowledge systems and cultural practices while fostering the restoration of positive learner's behaviour to reconnect with their cultural heritage and identities. Furthermore, Ubuntu promotes a holistic approach to learner discipline, emphasising respect, community, and restorative justice, which fosters inclusivity and ensures that both education and discipline reflect the diverse cultural realities of the learners.

In recent years, alarming reports of violence in South African secondary schools have become disturbingly common. Incidents where learners attack teachers or fellow learners are frequently highlighted in the media. [5] notes cases such as learners killing one another or, in some instances, killing teachers. [6] further details cases of learners throwing books or water at teachers and physical confrontations between learners and educators. In one instance, a disagreement over a cell phone resulted in a teacher slapping a learner. Additionally, a grade 11 boy was reported to have killed a primary school child. There have also been tragic instances where punitive measures by teachers led to the death of learners. These events underscore the severity of the current crisis in school discipline. Teachers across South Africa, particularly in the Tshwane West District, express deep concern over escalating behavioural issues in classrooms. Learner behaviour has been challenging for teachers, administrators, and parents alike [7]. Daily confrontations with unacceptable behaviour, often

involving threats or violence, make classroom management increasingly complex. The abolishment of corporal punishment further exacerbated these challenges, prompting the need for innovative disciplinary approaches. In response, the South African Schools Act 84 of 1996 introduced a code of conduct for learners, requiring governing bodies to develop these rules in consultation with stakeholders [8]. While the code of conduct aimed to address discipline, the persistence of behavioural issues, including gangsterism, demonstrates its ineffectiveness in many schools [9]. Ubuntu establishes a unique normative benchmark for social responsibility relevant to the prevention of conflicts and infection and provides a way to analyse ethical problems that might emerge in these contexts [10]. This article seeks to explore whether Ubuntu-guided discipline can provide a solution to these challenges. Specifically, it asks how Ubuntu-inspired discipline can be restored to improve learner behaviour in Gauteng secondary schools. The abolishment of corporal punishment has left a void in disciplinary measures, leading to the current behavioural degeneration. Therefore, this study aims to examine how Ubuntu-inspired discipline can be revitalised to address learner behaviour in Tshwane West District's secondary schools.

1.1 Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to explore the role of Ubuntu-inspired discipline in addressing behavioural challenges in Tshwane West District secondary schools. It aims to investigate how values such as empathy, respect, and community engagement can transform learner behaviour and foster a positive school environment. The study seeks to assess the effectiveness of Ubuntu principles like *imbizo* and *letsema* in promoting collaborative problem-solving and shared responsibility among educators, parents, and learners. Additionally, it intends to provide practical recommendations for integrating Ubuntu-inspired approaches into school policies to enhance discipline and improve academic outcomes.

1.2 Research question

The study seeks to answer the following question:

- How does Ubuntu-inspired discipline provide an alternative approach to addressing violent and disruptive behaviours among learners in Tshwane West District secondary schools?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Ubuntu-inspired discipline

Ubuntu is a time-honoured moral philosophy that continues to seek recognition within the broader spectrum of moral theories. This concept has proven its value in African societies as a guiding philosophy that promotes order and morality [2]. Numerous advocates of Ubuntu argue that it represents an essential aspect of human existence that must not be overlooked [11]. [2] describes Ubuntu as an inclusive African worldview grounded in moral principles such as humanness, care, sharing, respect, and dignity. These principles aim to foster a harmonious and high-quality communal life where individuals do not harm one another. The ethical guidelines inherent in Ubuntu promote both the avoidance of intentional harm and the conscientiousness to refrain from actions that could endanger others. Despite the efforts of Ubuntu scholars to establish its legitimacy as a moral theory, some critics challenge its credibility. [12] notes that numerous philosophers, political theorists, civil society activists, and human rights advocates in South Africa oppose this perspective of Ubuntu as a valid moral framework, citing its vagueness. Critics of the Africanist perspective argue that it presents various political, moral, epistemological, and educational shortcomings [2]. Consequently, they question Ubuntu's suitability as a foundation for democratic citizenship in South Africa. In response, [2] defends the potential of Ubuntu as a moral theory and public policy, asserting that its values are enshrined in the South African Constitution. He further counters scepticism regarding Ubuntu's practical applicability for citizenship, emphasising its historical role in adjudicating moral behaviour in African communities prior to colonial disruption. [8] advocates for Ubuntu as a moral theory, while [13] considers it a viable public policy. To effectively address indiscipline in schools, it is essential for all community members, including learners, to uphold ethical, honest, and honourable conduct. As an African philosophy, Ubuntu is deeply embedded in the moral values of African communities. [14] characterises Ubuntu as a communitarian philosophy that emphasises virtues like compassion, tolerance, and harmony.

The notion of Ubuntu is encapsulated in the saying “umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu (muthu ndi muthu nga vhatu),” meaning that a person is a person because of others. This highlights the importance of caring for one another and recognising that our humanity is diminished by

greed and oppression. [15] posits that South Africans view Ubuntu as both a moral quality and a philosophical worldview that emphasises interconnectedness. Ubuntu posits that to be fully human, individuals must be embedded in a community through relationships characterised by care and obligation. The justification for viewing Ubuntu as a moral theory informs the pursuit of a discipline inspired by its principles. According to Glasser's Choice Theory, learners choose their behaviour, which may sometimes be influenced by genetic factors, such as the need for survival, love and belonging, power, freedom, and enjoyment [16]. Although Choice Theory emphasises personal choice, the objective of discipline is to cultivate responsibility and self-control in learners by supporting their mental, emotional, and social development [17]. In this context, teachers play a crucial role in establishing relationships founded on mutual respect and trust, which are essential for fostering self-respect and adherence to school rules [18]. Ubuntu-inspired discipline is characterised by principles such as peace, respect, tolerance, discipline, sharing, and care. Implementing these principles can create a conducive environment for teaching and learning. In South Africa, Ubuntu is frequently referenced as a guiding principle for communities striving for harmony and interdependence [8]. Schools should prioritise fostering discipline to create an environment conducive to learning, with a focus on how Ubuntu can inform disciplinary practices. This study advocates for Ubuntu-inspired discipline rooted in the previously mentioned principles.

Effective Ubuntu-inspired discipline can take various forms. [19] notes that these methods include positive reinforcement, modelling behaviour, and creating loving, supportive environments at home or in school. Positive reinforcement frames discipline as a means of teaching self-control rather than mere control. When adults help children develop self-control, they effectively equip them with the skills needed for self-discipline [19]. Ubuntu-inspired discipline also emphasises positive outcomes, focusing on problem-solving and preventing the recurrence of inappropriate behaviour. Understanding the root causes of indiscipline is key to preventing its repetition. This is particularly relevant to the topic of "Ubuntu-Inspired Discipline: Restoring Learner Behavior in Gauteng Secondary Schools."

2.2 Learners' indiscipline in school

According to Glasser's Choice Theory, some learners choose to exhibit indiscipline, while others may inherit such behaviours from their parents. Studies have suggested that restoring learner indiscipline cannot be achieved only within schools, as parents play a pivotal role in

shaping, influencing, and significantly reducing behavioural issues. This perspective is supported by [16], who argue that indiscipline often arises from learners' attempts to satisfy their basic needs, including survival, love, belonging, power, freedom, and enjoyment. [20] suggests that the lack of discipline in schools may stem from various issues, including negative attitudes from teachers, parents who struggle to cover school fees, and political influences that allow principals to be controlled and manipulated. Additionally, ineffective or overly lenient principals may prioritise pleasing learners at the expense of staff, while negative peer influences can also play a significant role. Symptoms of indiscipline can manifest in various ways, including both peaceful and violent demonstrations, general unrest, mass disobedience, deliberate violations of school rules, drug use, delinquency, drunkenness, theft, truancy, absenteeism, persistent lateness, bullying, and laziness [20]. Among these, drug use has been specifically highlighted as a significant contributor to indiscipline. This context is particularly relevant to the discussion on "Ubuntu-Inspired Discipline: Restoring Learner Behavior in Gauteng Secondary Schools."

2.3 Restoration of Ubuntu-inspired discipline in secondary schools

To foster discipline within schools, it is essential to implement the principles and values of Ubuntu, such as peace, respect, care, empathy, morality, honesty, sharing, and tolerance [8]. A leadership style embodying these values can significantly enhance school discipline, ensuring effective teaching and learning. [11] argues that Ubuntu-inspired discipline fosters peace within schools, creating a conducive educational environment. [8] observes that communities have historically thrived in harmony and interdependence due to the favourable environments established by Ubuntu. He asserts that the philosophy of Ubuntu is fundamentally linked to school discipline, which hinges on mutual respect. [11] emphasises that "respect for oneself is crucial; if one does not respect oneself, how can one respect others?" Thus, peace, discipline, and respect are intertwined with the moral conduct of community members. Community members must embody ethical, honest, and honourable behaviour [13]. [8] not only views Ubuntu as a philosophy, but also recognises it as a moral theory. Empathy and compassion are also foundational pillars of Ubuntu that are essential for transforming the school environment into a space conducive to effective teaching and learning. This framework sets the stage for the discussion on Ubuntu-Inspired Discipline: Restoring Learner Behavior in Gauteng Secondary Schools.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is guided by Glasser's Choice Theory, a psychological model developed in 1998 to explain why individuals behave as they do and how they can form positive relationships with others. Glasser's Choice Theory serve as a valuable lens for understanding Ubuntu-inspired discipline in restoring learner behaviour in Gauteng secondary schools by emphasising the role of individual responsibility and the fulfilment of basic human needs [16]. The theory posits that all human behaviour is driven by the need to satisfy five fundamental needs: survival, love and belonging, power, freedom, and fun. These needs align with the communal values of Ubuntu, which focuses on interconnectedness, empathy, respect, and moral responsibility within a collective. These needs are rooted in human genetics, influencing behaviour across different environments. Survival, as expanded by [21], includes both physical safety and psychological security, while the need for love and belonging serves as the foundation for satisfying all other needs [22].

Glasser's Choice Theory posits that people are not externally motivated by rewards or punishments, but are instead driven by an internal quest to meet these essential needs [16]. Learners' behaviour, while influenced by heredity, is largely a result of their personal choices within their specific environments. [17] suggests that internal factors, such as hormones and metabolism, alongside external factors like gender and environmental conditions, also impact how these needs are expressed. For instance, exposure to drugs or chemicals in a learner's environment can alter their genetic expression, affecting behaviour. The core principle of Glasser's Choice Theory asserts that human behaviour is a means to satisfy these five universal needs. Through specific behaviours, individuals aim to achieve a "quality world" where they feel fulfilled by the people, experiences, and belief systems that align with their needs [23]. This framework suggests that addressing learners' behavioural issues requires a deeper understanding of their choices, and how these choices are influenced by the pursuit of their innate needs.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative approach rooted in ethnographic principles [24]. Ethnography, known for its deep cultural understanding, utilizes methods such as observation, exploratory conversations, mapping, and charting to simplify complex concepts. These techniques were essential in uncovering the lived experiences of individuals working to establish Ubuntu-inspired discipline to improve learner behaviour. By using this

methodology, the researchers explored the cultural and practical dimensions of discipline, aligning the study with the Ubuntu philosophy, which emphasizes community and interconnectedness. The four secondary schools selected for this study were purposefully chosen to provide diverse and contextually relevant insights. Schools A and B were selected because of their prominence in local media due to persistent learner misbehaviour, which presented disciplinary challenges. On the other hand, Schools C and D were recognized for their exemplary behavioural environments, serving as positive models. By including both schools with disciplinary challenges and those with positive behavioural outcomes, the study captured a wide range of experiences. This approach ensured the representativeness of the sample and provided a balanced exploration of the factors influencing learner behaviour across contrasting contexts. The principals from each school were also invited to participate, which enriched the data with leadership perspectives on disciplinary practices.

The sample consisted of 24 participants, distributed across four focus groups. Each group included one deputy principal, one head of department, two teachers, and two parents. Teachers were selected based on their experience (three or more years) on disciplinary committees, while parents were chosen for their active involvement in the School Governing Body (SGB) for at least two years. This purposeful selection was designed to ensure the inclusion of stakeholders with relevant expertise and experiences in implementing Ubuntu-inspired discipline, thereby enriching the study's understanding of the practices involved. For the data analysis, a thematic coding approach was employed. Initially, all focus group discussions were transcribed verbatim, and these transcripts were carefully reviewed to identify emerging themes and patterns

4.1 Data collection

The study employed qualitative data collection methods, including telephonic interviews, focus group discussions, and observations. These approaches are widely recognised in qualitative research for their effectiveness in gathering rich, detailed information. Data collection took place in the Tshwane West District of South Africa. Telephonic interviews, lasting approximately 50 minutes each, were conducted with the principals of the four selected schools. Following these interviews, focus group discussions were organised, consisting of deputy principals, heads of departments, teachers, and parents from the selected schools. Each focus group comprised six participants and lasted approximately 60 minutes. In addition to engaging with human participants, the study included the analysis of relevant

documents, specifically school policies related to discipline. This multi-faceted approach resulted in data triangulation, combining insights from interviews, discussions, and document analysis. Triangulation allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter by mitigating the limitations of a single method and enhancing the validity of the findings in accordance with ethical standards [25]. This robust data collection process supports the exploration of "Ubuntu-Inspired Discipline: Restoring Learner Behavior in Gauteng Secondary Schools."

4.2 Data analysis

Following data collection, a comparative and interpretive data analysis was initiated. Field notes were transcribed, capturing reflections on impressions, relationships, and coherence observed during the data collection process. This text was subsequently organised into broad themes, from which specific categories and sub-categories emerged through an interactive and inductive coding process [26]. The analysis considered participants' social contexts, allowing for the identification of patterns in existing norms, beliefs, and values within the original categories. This approach facilitated reflections on the presence or absence of Ubuntu among principals, departmental heads, teachers, and learners striving to enhance discipline in their schools. The data analysis yielded several key findings, including insights into learner behaviour, school policies on discipline, the causes of learner misbehaviour, the choices behind behaviours, the influence of heredity, and the impact of Ubuntu-inspired discipline on improving learner behaviour [27]. These findings provide a comprehensive understanding of how Ubuntu principles can be implemented to revitalise learner behaviour in Gauteng secondary schools, forming the foundation of the study titled "Ubuntu-Inspired Discipline: Restoring Learner Behavior in Gauteng Secondary Schools."

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Resistance to Change

One of the primary challenges in adopting Ubuntu-inspired discipline is resistance from educators, parents, and learners who may be accustomed to more traditional, punitive approaches. Shifting from a punishment-based system to a more empathetic and restorative approach requires substantial cultural and mindset changes. Some stakeholders may find it difficult to embrace this shift, particularly if they do not fully understand the principles of Ubuntu or if they believe that such methods do not yield immediate results

5.2 Inadequate Training and Knowledge

Effective implementation of Ubuntu-inspired discipline requires comprehensive training for teachers, school leaders, and parents to ensure they understand the underlying principles and how to apply them in practice. Without proper training, there is a risk that Ubuntu principles may be misinterpreted or inconsistently applied, limiting their effectiveness. Schools without access to professional development programs focused on Ubuntu principles may struggle to foster the necessary skills to integrate these practices into everyday disciplinary actions.

5.3 Resource Limitations: Implementing

Ubuntu-inspired discipline may require additional resources, such as time, personnel, and materials. In schools with limited financial or human resources, it may be challenging to create and sustain the community-building activities (such as imbizos) or the regular, structured dialogue between teachers, parents, and learners that Ubuntu-inspired discipline requires. Resource constraints could hinder the thorough implementation of these practices, making them less effective.

5.4 Lack of Clear Policy Frameworks

Although some schools have established codes of conduct, there may be a lack of clear, context-specific policies that integrate Ubuntu principles into school discipline. In schools where disciplinary policies are not tailored to include values of empathy, respect, and interdependence, there could be confusion or inconsistency in how discipline is applied. Additionally, without legal backing or alignment with national education policies, it may be challenging for schools to fully implement Ubuntu-inspired discipline effectively.

5.5 Cultural and Contextual Barriers

While Ubuntu values align with South African cultural norms, their practical application can be hindered by the diverse and sometimes conflicting cultural and socio-economic backgrounds of learners, parents, and educators. In multicultural environments, different communities may have varying interpretations of what Ubuntu means, which could affect their acceptance and application of these principles. Moreover, learners from challenging socio-economic backgrounds may bring behaviours rooted in external pressures that cannot be easily addressed through Ubuntu-inspired practices alone.

5.6 Time Constraints:

Implementing a comprehensive Ubuntu-inspired approach may require more time than traditional disciplinary methods. Educators and school leaders may struggle to allocate sufficient time for dialogue, reflection, and community-building activities, especially in schools with large numbers of learners or high demands on staff time. This can result in a superficial application of Ubuntu principles or the prioritization of immediate results over long-term behavioural change.

5.7 Inconsistent Support Across Stakeholders

For Ubuntu-inspired discipline to succeed, all stakeholders—including school staff, parents, and the broader community—must be aligned in their commitment to the approach. In some cases, lack of buy-in or inconsistent participation from parents or community members may undermine efforts to foster a cooperative, values-driven school culture. If some stakeholders are not fully engaged or are sceptical of Ubuntu principles, the overall impact of the discipline model may be diminished.

5.8 Mitigation Strategies:

To address these challenges, it is essential to establish robust training programs for all stakeholders, promote ongoing awareness campaigns to build understanding of Ubuntu's values, and ensure that school policies are contextually relevant and well-implemented. Schools can seek external support, such as partnerships with local organizations, to help alleviate resource constraints. Additionally, incorporating Ubuntu into school leadership's vision, and actively involving parents and the wider community, will create a more collaborative and sustainable implementation framework. By acknowledging these challenges and developing strategies to overcome them, the potential for Ubuntu-inspired discipline to transform learner behaviour becomes more attainable.

6 SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study identifies several barriers, such as resistance to change, inadequate training, and a lack of resources, which hinder the successful adoption of Ubuntu-inspired discipline practices. To address resistance, it is crucial to implement awareness campaigns that emphasize the benefits of Ubuntu principles in restoring discipline and improving learner behaviour. These campaigns could include workshops and community engagements that showcase successful case studies, helping to foster a deeper understanding of Ubuntu's

relevance in contemporary school settings. To overcome the challenge of inadequate training, it is recommended that continuous professional development programs be designed specifically for educators, school leaders, and parents, focusing on Ubuntu-inspired discipline practices. These training programs should equip all stakeholders with the necessary skills to implement inclusive and culturally resonant disciplinary measures. The development of training modules that include conflict resolution, restorative practices, and effective communication strategies will be instrumental in addressing the gap in knowledge and practice. Resource limitations can be mitigated by advocating for external funding and partnerships with local organizations, which could support the implementation of Ubuntu-inspired discipline. Additionally, schools can leverage technology to enhance communication between teachers, parents, and learners, ensuring that information on disciplinary practices and expectations is readily available and accessible. Utilizing digital platforms for regular updates, feedback, and discussions will facilitate continuous engagement and collaboration among all stakeholders.

Furthermore, fostering a culture of collaboration within the school community is key. Schools should prioritize the establishment of regular meetings between educators, parents, and learners, where they can discuss challenges, share solutions, and refine discipline strategies. Creating structured spaces for ongoing dialogue about discipline and learner behaviour will promote collective ownership and responsibility for maintaining a positive school environment.

7 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study highlights the significance of Ubuntu-inspired discipline in addressing learner behaviour challenges within Tshwane West District secondary schools. Grounded in principles such as *imbizo* (community gatherings) and *letsema* (collaborative work), this approach emphasises social cohesion, respect, and shared responsibility among stakeholders. By integrating these values into school management practices, Ubuntu-inspired discipline offers a culturally relevant framework for fostering a positive and inclusive school environment. To enhance its effectiveness, school leaders must receive training that deepens their understanding of Ubuntu principles and equips them to apply these values in leadership and discipline strategies. This training should emphasise the importance of moral responsiveness and sensitivity to the needs of all stakeholders, creating an atmosphere conducive to both teaching and learning. Community engagement is a critical component of

this approach, which helps address the root causes of learner misbehaviour through collaborative solutions and shared accountability. Schools should prioritise the development of tailored, context-specific policies that reflect Ubuntu values and actively involve parents, educators, and learners in their implementation. While Ubuntu-inspired discipline offers significant promise, future research should explore its potential limitations to ensure a balanced and comprehensive understanding of its impact. By addressing behavioural challenges holistically, Tshwane West District schools can create nurturing environments that promote personal growth, academic success, and community well-being.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Ngubane, N., & Makua, M. (2021). Ubuntu pedagogy—transforming educational practices in South Africa through an African philosophy: From theory to practice. *Inkanyiso: Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 13(1), 1–12.
- [2] Letseka, M. (2012). In defence of Ubuntu. *Studies in Philosophy and Education*, 31, 47–60. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11217-011-9267-2>
- [3] Van Breda, A. D. (2019). Developing the notion of Ubuntu as African theory for social work practice. *Social Work*, 55(4), 439–450. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15270/52-2-762>
- [4] Chigangaidze, R. K., Matanga, A. A., & Katsuro, T. R. (2022). Ubuntu philosophy as a humanistic-existential framework for the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 62(3), 319–333. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00221678211044554>
- [5] Ukpokodu, O. N. (2016). *You can't teach us if you don't know us and care about us: Becoming an ubuntu, responsive and responsible urban teacher*. Peter Lang International Academic Publishers.
- [6] Ramphele, L. (2024). Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the development of cognitive and motor skills of Grade R learners. <http://hdl.handle.net/11660/12603>

- [7] Maphanga, N. P., Morojele, P. J., & Motsa, N. D. (2018). Gender dynamics in children's cross-sex relationships: A case from a South African farm school. *Gender and Behaviour*, 16(3), 11854–11869. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC-135714af19>
- [8] Porter, L. (2020). *Student behaviour: Theory and practice for teachers*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003117520>
- [9] Bray, E. (2005). Codes of conduct in public schools: A legal perspective. *South African Journal of Education*, 25(3), 133–138.
- [10] Sambala, E. Z., Cooper, S., & Manderson, L. (2019). Ubuntu as a framework for ethical decision making in Africa: Responding to epidemics. *Ethics & Behavior*, 30(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2019.1583565>
- [11] Setlhodi, I. I. (2018). Ubuntu leadership: An African panacea for improving school performance. *Africa Education Review*, 16(2), 126–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18146627.2018.1464885>
- [12] Metz, T. (2011). Ubuntu as a moral theory and human rights in South Africa. *African Human Rights Law Journal*, 11(2), 532–559. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC51951>
- [13] Chisale, S. S. (2018.) Ubuntu as care: Deconstructing the gendered Ubuntu. *Verbum et Ecclesia* 39(1), a1790. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ve.v39i1.1790>
- [14] West, A. (2014). Ubuntu and business ethics: Problems, perspectives and prospects. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 121(1), 47–61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-013-1669-3>
- [15] Msila, V. (2009). Ubuntu and peace-making in schools. *International Journal of Educational Policies*, 3(1), 51–66.
- [16] Mashayekh, R., & Shangarffam, N. (2021). The effect of choice theory-based instruction on EFL learners' speaking complexity, accuracy, and fluency. *International Journal of English and Education*, 10(2), 1-13
- [17] Jarada, T. N., Rokne, J. G., & Alhaji, R. (2020). A review of computational drug repositioning: Strategies, approaches, opportunities, challenges, and directions. *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 12, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-020-00450-7>

- [18] Sadik, F. (2018). Children and discipline: Investigating secondary school students' perception of discipline through metaphors. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 7(1), 31–44. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.7.1.31>
- [19] Darling-Hammond, L., & Cook-Harvey, C. M. (2018). *Educating the whole child: Improving school climate to support student success*. Learning Policy Institute.
- [20] Mwaniki, S. G. (2018). Students' indiscipline: A reflection on the causes of misbehavior among learners in Kenyan secondary schools. *Global Journal of Advanced Research*, 5(4), 171–177.
- [20] Mwaniki, S. (2018). Students' indiscipline: A reflection on the causes of misbehavior among learners in Kenyan secondary schools. *Global Journal of Advanced Research*, 5(6), 171-177.
- [21] Irvine, J. (2015). Enacting Glasser's (1998) Choice Theory in a grade 3 classroom: A case study. *Journal of Case Studies in Education*, 7. <http://www.aabri.com>
- [22] Lynch, M. (2016). Understanding three key classroom management theories. [03/29], <https://www.theedadvocate.org/understanding-three-key-classroom-management-theories/>.
- [23] Robey, P. A., Wubbolding, R. E., & Malters, M. (2017). A comparison of Choice Theory and Reality Therapy to Adlerian Individual Psychology. *The Journal of Individual Psychology* 73(4), 283–294. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1353/jip.2017.0024>
- [24] Mouton, J. (2001). *How to succeed in your master's and doctoral studies: A South African guide and resource book*. Van Schaik.
- [25] Khamis, T., & Khamis, A. (2020). The Aga Khan University and the sustainable development goals: Building on international partnerships to promote excellence. In *University Partnerships for Sustainable Development* (vol. 20, pp. 121-132). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- [26] McMillan, J. H., & Schumacher, S. (2010). *Research in education: Evidence-based inquiry*. Pearson.
- [27] Mabula, M. J., Khalabai, M. E., & Simeon, M. (2023). Factors impacting provisioning of learner textbooks in Tshwane North District schools, Gauteng Province, South Africa. *Open Access Library Journal*, 10(1), 1–17. DOI: 10.4236/oalib.1109523

[28] Raymond, E. (2017). The relationship between management strategies for learner discipline and learner discipline legal framework: A South African perspective. *Ponte International Journal of Science and Research*, 73(8).

[29] Mamaile, D., & Omodan, B. I. (2023). Exploring challenges hindering teachers' implementation of classroom management strategies in Gauteng High Schools, South Africa. *Research in Educational Policy and Management*, 5(2), 245–262. <https://doi.org/10.46303/repam.2023.22>